

THE SPREAD AND DAMAGE OF MONILIASIS DISEASE IN HAWTHORN PLANT

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Abstract. *In this article, according to the observation of moniliasis disease in hawthorn in Tashkent and Kashkadarya region, the moniliasis disease in Pontika variety of hawthorn, flower, rosette, leaf, branch fruit is observed up to 19.0 - 22.5%, the development of the disease is 10.8 - 11.2%.*

Keywords: *hawthorn moniliasis disease - (Monilia fructigena), Disease progression, Turkistan Karolkova, Pontika.*

Introduction. Today, the use of fruit and berry plants in agriculture and medicine is of particular interest. Solving these issues is carried out by comprehensive study of local and introduced plants. Cultivation of species introduced to new natural and climatic conditions leads to changes in the rhythm of seasonal development of plants, the nature of fruiting, seeds and vegetative regeneration, and other biological characteristics. Medicinal properties of hawthorn have been used since the 16th century. In the 19th century, a tincture made from its flowers and leaves were used as a blood purifier, and at first, hawthorn berries and flowers were recommended as a medicine for heart and blood vessel diseases.[5]

Hawthorn is widely cultivated as a fruit crop in many countries of the world: Spain, Algeria, Italy, etc., and in China it ranks third after apples and pears. In Russia, hawthorn still has no industrial value, but the therapeutic and nutritional properties of hawthorn fruits are well known.

In nature, hawthorn usually grows singly or in groups, in thickets along river banks, in thickets on mountain and mountain slopes, and rarely in sparse forests. It does not grow at all in densely growing trees.

They are not demanding on the soil, but they develop better in deep, moderately moist, well-drained fertile soils, they respond positively to the presence of lime in the soil. In Oda, they are simple, winter-hardy and light-loving.

Hawthorn trees are mainly affected by the following diseases of regional importance: 1. Hawthorn powdery mildew - (*Podosphaera oxyacanthae* de. Bary. f. *crataegi* Jacz. and *Phyllactinia suffulta* Sacc. f. *oxyacanthae* Roum.), 2 Brown spot – (*Septoria crataegicola* Bond, et Tram.), 3. Tracheomic disease of hawthorn – (*Fusarium oxysporum*),

4. Hawthorn rust disease - (*Gymno sporangium clavariaeforme*.),

5. Hawthorn white spot disease - (*Septoria crataegi* Kickx.),

6. Hawthorn moniliasis disease - (*monilial fructi* Gena). [5]

Moniliasis fungal disease can damage not only seed-bearing trees, but also various parts of fruit-bearing trees. Moniliasis develops when spring is rainy and warm. The plant damages the flower part, brown spots remain on the crop. The mycelium of the fungus passes from the inflorescence to the branches. Infected hawthorn flowers wither, some dry up and fall off. Infected branches turn brown, oval or ellipse-shaped lesions appear. The leaves on the infected branch change color and fade.

The disease begins with the appearance of small circular spots on the fruits, the tissues under the spots begin to be damaged, the affected fruit does not swell and begins to harden. Infected fruits hang on the trees, remain on the tree until early spring, in some cases they may dry up and fall to the ground. (1-2 photos)

Fungal conidia of Moniliasis are dry and passively spread by birds, insects, wind and air currents. Spores of infected fruit debris left on the tree help spread the disease.

Picture 1.

Picture 2.

Research methods. Researches on the study of fungal diseases in hawthorn were carried out on the basis of generally accepted methods in mycology and agricultural phytopathology. Species composition, bioecology of pathogenic fungi were studied by N.M. Pidoplichko, M.K. Khokhryakov; infection with diseases and the development of the disease were carried out with the help of methodological manuals of K.M. Stepanov, A. YE. Chumakov, I. I. Minkevich (1974) [1, 2, 3, 4.].

Research results.

According to observation of moniliasis disease in hawthorn at Bostonliq mountain experimental station, Bostonliq district, Tashkent region, the number of flowers, inflorescences, leaves, branches and fruits of hawthorn of the Turkestan variety is 20.3%, the development of the disease is 10.7 %. Hawthorn with moniliasis disease consists in 19.3% of flowers, buds, leaves, and fruits of the Karolkova variety, and the development of the disease is 10.5%. With moniliasis disease of Pontica hawthorn variety, flower, rosette, leaf, branch fruit is 19.0%, the development of the disease is 10.8%.

In Burchimula Forestry, Bostonliq District, Tashkent Region, moniliasis disease in hawthorn is observed in 23.0% of flowers, inflorescences, leaves, branches and fruits of hawthorn Turkestan variety, the development of the disease is 11.7%. 22.7% of flowers, inflorescences, leaves, and fruits of the Karolkova variety is observed, disease development is 11.5%. With

moniliasis disease of Pontica hawthorn variety, flower, rosette, leaf, branch and fruit are 23.3%, the development of the disease is 11.8%.

According to monitoring of moniliasis disease in hawthorn in Yakkabog forest farm, Yakkabog district, Kashkadarya region, the number of flowers, buds, leaves, branches and fruits of Hawthorn Turkestan variety is 22.2%, the development of the disease is 11.4 %. 22.3% of flowers, inflorescences, leaves, and fruits of the Karolkova variety is observed, disease development is 11.3%. With moniliasis disease of Pontica hawthorn variety, flower, rosette, leaf, branch fruit is 22.5%, the development of the disease is 11.2%.

Moniliasis disease in hawthorn varieties spread and damage 2023

Number	The location of the study	Area, ga	variety	Organs of plant	2023 year	
					Damage %	Development of disease, %
1.	Bostonliq mountain scientific-experimental station, Bostonliq district, Tashkent region	10	Turkistan	Flower leaf, branch fruit	20,3	10,7
			Karolkova	Flower leaf, branch fruit	19,3	10,5
			Pontika	Flower leaf, branch fruit	19,0	10,8
2.	Burchimula forestry, Bostonliq district, Tashkent region	20	Turkistan	Flower leaf, branch fruit	23,0	11,7
			Karolkova	Flower leaf, branch fruit	22,7	11,5
			Pontika	Flower leaf, branch fruit	23,3	11,8
3.	Yakkabog Forestry, Yakkabog District, Kashkadarya Region	15	Turkistan	Flower leaf, branch fruit	22,2	11,4
			Karolkova	Flower leaf, branch fruit	22,3	11,3
			Pontika	Flower leaf, branch fruit	22,5	11,2

Summary: According to observation of moniliasis disease in hawthorn at the Bostonliq mountain scientific-experimental station, Bostonliq district, Tashkent region, flowers, inflorescences, leaves, and fruit of hawthorn have 19.0% of moniliasis disease of the Turkestan variety, the development of the disease is 10.8%. According to monitoring of moniliasis disease in hawthorn in Yakkabog district, Kashkadarya region, flower, rosette, leaf, branch fruit of Hawthorn Pontika variety have 22.5% of moniliasis disease, the development of the disease is 11.2%.

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